

**FABRICATION AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF
METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

Most MMC fabrication is carried out by melt infiltration or by powder routes. A brief survey is given of information on relationships between processing conditions and composite microstructure for these two types of process. Data are presented from analyses of both mechanical and thermal aspects of squeeze-infiltration, together with implications for fibre damage and matrix grain structure. Factors affecting fibre-matrix bond strength are then briefly covered for a range of processes.

NOMENCLATURE

(a) <u>Parameters</u>	
d	(m) Distance between centres of adjacent parallel fibres within an in-plane layer
e	(-) Nominal compressive strain of preform
E	(Pa) Young's modulus of fibre
f	(-) Volume of fibres classified as "crosslinking" as a fraction of the total volume of fibres
h	(m) Distance between layers of in-plane fibres
H	($Wm^{-2}K^{-1}$) Heat transfer coefficient at melt-die interface
L	(m) Mean length of "crosslinking" fibres between anchorage points in successive layers
P	(Pa) Pressure (applied to melt)
r	(m) Radius of fibres
s	(-) Spacing ratio between interlayer and intralayer fibre separations
t	(s) Time
T	(K) Temperature

V	(-)	Volume fraction
w	(N)	Force normal to the layer plane acting at all crossover points in a layer
W	(N)	Force normal to the layer plane acting on the end of a "crosslinking" fibre, anchored in an in-plane layer
z	(m)	Dimension in direction of infiltration (normal to fibre plane)
α	(-)	Back-diffusion coefficient for solute during solidification
γ	(J m ⁻²)	Melt-atmosphere interfacial energy
δ	(m)	Change in thickness of an in-plane layer on application of a stress
Δ	(m)	Change in interlayer spacing on application of a stress
θ	(radians)	Mean angle which "crosslinking" fibres make with the in-plane layers
σ	(Pa)	Stress in fibre
ϕ	(-)	Sine of the inclination angle θ

(b) Subscripts

a - applied	i - infiltration	p - in-plane
c - crosslinking	L - liquidus	P - preform
f - fibre	m - melt	r - relaxation
F - fracture	M - maximum	s - solid
	0 - initial (relaxed) value	

INTRODUCTION

A variety of techniques are currently being employed to manufacture MMCs. These include diffusion bonding [1], superplastic forming [2], comocasting [3], spray forming [4], melt infiltration [5] and powder processing [6]. The last two of these are the most widely employed and this article attempts to review a few of the salient features associated with different variants of these two approaches. The information presented is limited to observations on relationships between processing conditions and resultant microstructures, although some implications for the performance of the product are mentioned in places.

EXPERIMENTAL

The squeeze-infiltration process has been investigated using a setup [5],[7] in which the molten alloy is poured into a cylindrical die cavity containing a fibrous preform, either filling the section of the die, or held within a further cylindrical container. A hydrostatic pressure is then applied to this melt via a hydraulic ram, with both the applied pressure and the ram displacement being monitored, in addition to the thermal field in the die cavity and die base. The device can be operated in a controlled atmosphere chamber.

A variety of powder processing techniques have been employed. These normally involve premixing of metallic powder with fibrous (or particulate) ceramic material, using either wet or dry blending, an operation which can be carried out under controlled atmosphere. This is followed by cold and/or hot pressing to form a billet, which can then be processed by a variety of routes, including rolling, extrusion or die-casting [8].

INFILTRATION AND FIBRE DAMAGE

The various phenomena involved in the squeeze-infiltration process have been examined by several authors [5],[9]-[11]. Entry of the melt into the fibrous array is opposed by the necessity of generating meniscus curvature at the infiltration front, requiring a pressure increment

$$P_i = \sum_i \gamma / r_j \quad (1)$$

where r_j are the principal radii of curvature and γ is the interfacial energy at the melt-atmosphere interface. A lower limit on r_j will be half the inter-fibre spacing: although wetting of the fibres by the melt would allow passage with reduced curvature, it's worth noting that there may in practice be insufficient time for repeated establishment of wetting conditions during progressive penetration. Application of eq.(1) to a parallel fibre bundle (hexagonally packed) suggests that, for example, with a γ value corresponding to pure Al [12], 15 μm diameter fibres, occupying about 75 vol% of space, could be infiltrated by a modest applied pressure of about 1 MPa (10 atm). This is valid for axial infiltration, and such aligned composites are routinely produced this way. However, the experimentally more convenient arrangement of transverse infiltration introduces a complication, in that inter-fibre spacings can be sharply reduced by the applied pressure: in practice, such infiltration is often difficult with metallic melts.

Figure 1 Scanning electron micrograph showing the distribution of fibres in a (planar random) preform ($V_f = 12\%$)

The case of a planar random array of fibres is of interest both because it is not so prone to the above problem of transverse compression and in view of other advantages associated with ease of preform preparation and reduced property anisotropies. Process modelling is now complicated by the greater geometrical complexity, illustrated in the preform structure of Fig.1. A possible approach to describing this structure is shown in Fig.2(a), where

Figure 2 Models of (a) fibre distribution and (b) fibre bending within a preform

all fibres are classified as either "in-plane" or "crosslinking" (the fraction in the second category being given the symbol f). Two further parameters are needed to define the structure and these may be chosen as the "spacing ratio" $s_o (= h_o/d)$ and the crosslink angle θ (assumed equal for all fibres), conveniently specified by $\phi (= \sin \theta = h_o/L)$. It is then easily shown [11] that the infiltration pressure is given by

$$P_i = 2\gamma / [r([\pi/(2s_o V_f(1-f))]^{1/2} - 1)] \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, this geometrical model can be used to predict preform deformation and fibre damage, based on the elastic deflection analysis shown in Fig.2(b). Both interlayer and intralayer compressions arise from simple bending of cylindrical beams, the compliances of these two deformations being additive to give the preform compliance. Application of elementary theory for a cantilever and a simply supported beam gives [11] predicted stress-strain relationships for interlayer and intralayer strains respectively

$$e_c = [8\pi s_o (1-\phi^2) / (3E V_f^2 (1-f) f \phi^4)] P_a \quad (3)$$

$$e_p = [4\pi(2\pi)^{1/2} / 9E (s_o V_f (1-f))^{5/2}] P_a \quad (4)$$

On summing these two compliances, a preform compliance is obtained and this can be compared with experimental stress-strain curves for (dry) compression of preforms. Comparisons [11] for different V_f values gave

good agreement at low strain (using values of the three parameters f , s_0 and ϕ in the expected ranges), for the case of high aspect ratio δ -alumina fibres. Finally, the onset of fibre fracture can also be described with this model, using a simple comparison between the maximum stress in the fibre and a published failure stress value σ_F . Substitution and rearrangement allows [11] prediction of the applied pressure at the onset of fracture of the crosslinking fibres

$$P_{aFc} = f\phi^2 V_f [V_f(1-f)/(2\pi s_0(1-\phi^2))]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sigma_F / 4 \quad (5)$$

Using these equations, a crude indication may be obtained of likely infiltration characteristics. For example, up to V_f values of 40-50%, 20 μm diameter fibres need infiltration pressures of only an atmosphere or so, but submicron whiskers might need many tens of atmospheres. The deformation and fracture behaviour is predicted to be independent of fibre diameter (although modulus and fracture stress values may, of course, be different for finer fibres): there is thus a prediction that fibre fracture is more likely to be preceded (and thus precluded) by melt infiltration when the fibres are coarse. In addition, the value of V_f is significant because fracture and infiltration exhibit different dependence on this parameter. This is illustrated in Fig.3, which shows the variations for a 3 μm diameter fibre, using some typical parameter data. This indicates that infiltration should take place without fibre damage for the V_f range of interest (10-40%), which is consistent with experimental observation.

Figure 3 Predicted dependence of (a) applied pressure and (b) preform strain, for the onset of melt infiltration and fibre fracture, on fibre volume fraction.

Fig.3(b) suggests that this infiltration may be preceded by a significant elastic preform deformation of several %. Depending on V_f , these equations suggest that it may be difficult to avoid fibre damage with a preform of fine (submicron) whiskers, although it may be useful to note the possibility of significantly reducing the value of γ (and hence P_i) by selected solute addition to the melt. In practice, infiltration of whisker preforms tends to require large pressures and often causes damage [13].

GRAIN STRUCTURE

Squeeze-infiltrated composites often exhibit a fine grain size. Although this may in some cases be due to preferential crystal nucleation on fibre surfaces, it should be noted that, even in the absence of such an effect, thermal conditions tend to favour a fine-grained structure. For example, with the ICI "Saffil" 3 μm diameter δ -alumina fibre, local thermal equilibration between melt and fibre is very rapid, leading to pronounced chilling of the melt. Squeeze-infiltrated composites of this fibre in an aluminium-based matrix have a fine grain size, despite the demonstrated absence of any preferential nucleation on fibre surfaces. These characteristics give rise to structures such as the one shown in Fig.4, a longitudinal section from near the top of the reinforced region. The sharp transition in grain size occurs at a level thought to correspond approximately to the top of the preform at the point of infiltration (before elastic recovery of the fibrous array).

Figure 4 Optical micrograph of a longitudinal section from an Al-2.5 wt%Mg/18 vol% Al_2O_3 composite near the top of the preform.

An obvious inference is that the fine-grained region corresponds to that portion of the melt chilled by heat exchange with the fibres, so that solidification occurred in this portion of the casting with a higher growth velocity and/or lower thermal gradient. However, finite difference modelling of the heat flow [11],[14],[15] has suggested a slightly different explanation. The thermal profiles shown in Fig.5 indicate that the thermal discontinuity at the point of infiltration ($t=0$) is rapidly smoothed out by conductive heat flow (in a metal of high thermal diffusivity, such as Al), so that an advancing solidification front would experience no change in growth conditions at the height concerned. The most likely explanation would seem to be that the pronounced chilling of the melt close behind the infiltration front generates a large number of small crystallites throughout the preform. Fragments lifted up with the relaxing preform would tend to be remelted as the array entered hotter liquid, but many of the solid particles in the lower portion might survive and grow into individual grains as cooling occurs.

Figure 5 Predictions from the finite difference model of the thermal profiles across the solidifying system at different periods after infiltration is complete.

FIBRE-MATRIX INTERFACE AND OXIDE FILMS

Squeeze-infiltration tends to favour formation of a strong interfacial bond. Fig.6 is a back-scattered SEM image showing solute-rich (copper in this case) regions surrounding the fibres. This arises because the last-solidifying liquid collects around the fibres, where contact occurs under high hydrostatic pressure for an appreciable period. The duration of this contact will depend on microsegregation characteristics, as well as thermal conditions. For example, under the conditions modelled in Fig.5, which refers to an Al-Mg alloy, the melt contact time extends to a few minutes: for much of this period the melt is significantly enriched in solute (Mg).

Figure 6 Scanning electron micrograph (back-scattered image) of an Al-4.5 wt%Cu/18 vol% Al_2O_3 composite, showing copper enhancement around the fibres.

Figure 7 Fracture surfaces of (a) Al-2.5 wt%Mg/18 vol% Al_2O_3 and (b) Pure Al (99.97%)/18 vol% Al_2O_3

This would appear to favour strong bonding, particularly for solutes that segregate to give relatively low melting point liquids, but chemical reactivity also appears to play a role. For example, Mg solute has been shown [10] to take part in a limited chemical reaction on the surface of Saffil fibres and this can apparently enhance the fibre-matrix bond strength. This effect is illustrated by the two fracture surfaces shown in Fig.7: these composites were produced under identical conditions, except for the presence of magnesium in the melt in one case. Although individual reactions taking place, (and their effects on the interfacial bond strength) will be specific to the systems concerned, it is worth noting how squeeze infiltration appears to favour intimate fibre-matrix contact without promoting prolonged reaction and consequent thick, brittle product layers.

A further point of interest concerns the formation and distribution of oxide films. It might be expected that an (aluminium) infiltration front would always carry an oxide film of some type, which would be deposited on the fibres. However, it has been found [10] that no such layer of appreciable thickness is in fact present in these composites. This turns out to be consistent with a simple analysis of oxygen availability, when account is taken of the vast surface area presented by an array of fine fibres and the high speed of infiltration. The absence of oxidation problems is generally a feature of the squeeze-infiltration process, although there may nevertheless be advantages in controlled atmosphere operation for certain melts.

Figure 8 Fracture surfaces from Al-10 wt%Mg/10 vol% Al_2O_3 composites produced by powder routes involving consolidation (a) by hot pressing above T_L (b) by die-casting as a semisolid slurry.

In contrast to this situation, the presence of oxide films can be a significant factor inhibiting good fibre-matrix bonding with powder fabrication routes. For example, Fig.8(a) shows a fracture surface from the composite produced by hot pressing of a powder preform at a temperature above the liquidus of the alloy concerned: apparently, the surface oxide films on the (air-atomised) metallic particles have to some extent survived this operation and appear to be responsible for the relatively poor matrix-fibre cohesion. The solution to this problem often lies in the introduction of plastic shear strain during the consolidation operation, in order to disperse the oxide. Recent experiments [8],[16] have shown that die-casting, with a charge composed of a semisolid slurry containing dispersed ceramic fibres, can achieve this effect. Fig.8(b) shows a fracture surface from such a casting, from which it appears that oxide film dispersal has been successful.

A more conventional consolidation technique introducing the necessary shear strain is that of extrusion. This is normally done in the fully solid state, as tensile stresses in the die exit region will otherwise tend to cause defects as a result of hot shortness. Unfortunately, conventional extrusion of a powder compact containing ceramic fibres tends to cause fibre damage and inhomogeneity of fibre distribution [17]. This can lead in extreme cases to severe "banding" of fibre distribution, of the type shown in Fig.9. Such bunching of fibres is potentially at least as deleterious as a reduction in mean aspect ratio, even when fibre-matrix bonding is strong. Only recently has work been reported [18] aimed at modifying extrusion conditions so as to improve fibre integrity and distribution homogeneity.

Figure 9 Optical micrograph of a longitudinal section from an Al-10 wtMg/18 vol% Al_2O_3 composite produced by powder compaction and extrusion at 500°C with a shear face die and an extrusion ratio of 20.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

(i) Squeeze-infiltration of a fibrous preform can be analysed for different preform geometries in terms of applied pressure, elastic deformation and the onset of fibre fracture. Aligned bundles can be infiltrated axially with high volume fractions of ceramic. Fibre damage may occur with planar random fibre arrays, particularly with fine (submicron) fibres.

(ii) Squeeze-infiltration tends to lead to a fine grain structure in most of the composite, although sharp transitions to a coarse columnar structure have been observed. With an aluminium/ δ -alumina combination, these observations have been explained in terms of heat flow characteristics, with no preferential crystal nucleation on fibre surfaces.

(iii) The strength of the fibre-matrix bond has been examined for several processes. Squeeze-infiltration promotes relatively prolonged contact between fibre surface and a (solute-enriched) melt under high hydrostatic pressure. This tends to be conducive to strong bonding, although interfacial chemistry can also be important. The presence of oxide films can inhibit intimate bonding for powder premixing and consolidation routes, although this can be avoided if substantial plastic shear strain is introduced. This can be achieved in processes such as extrusion, although fibre damage and distribution inhomogeneities may result. The presence of liquid during shearing can be beneficial and promising structures have been produced by pressure die-casting of semisolid slurries made by powder premixing and compaction.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Smith, P.R. and Froes, F.H., "Developments in Titanium Metal Matrix Composites", J. of Metals, March 1984, **36**, 19-26
- [2] Lloyd, D., "Fabrication of Fibre Composites using an aluminium superplastic alloy as matrix" J. Mat.Sci. 1984, **19**, 2488-2492
- [3] Quigley, B.F., Abbaschian, G.J., Wunderlin, R. and Mehrabian, R., "A method for Fabrication of Aluminium-Alumina Composites", Metall. Trans. A, 1982, **13A**, 93-100
- [4] Westfall, J., "Arc Spray Fabrication of Metal Matrix Composite Monotape", US Patent Appl SN 560035, 1985
- [5] Clyne, T.W. and Bader, M.G., "Analysis of a Squeeze-Infiltration Process for Fabrication of Metal Matrix Composites". In 5th International Conference on Composite Materials, ed. W.C. Harrigan et al., TMS-AIME, 1985, pp.755-771

- [6] Young, R.M.K. and Clyne, T.W., "A Powder Mixing and Preheating Route to Slurry Production for Semisolid Die casting". Powder Metall., 1986, **29**, 195-99
- [7] Clyne, T.W., Bader, M.G., Cappleman, G.R. and Hubert, P.A., "The use of a δ -alumina fibre for metal matrix composites", J. Mat. Sci., 1985 **20**, 85-96
- [8] Young, R.M.K. and Clyne, T.W., "A powder-based approach to semisolid processing of metals for fabrication of die-castings and composites: J. Mat. Sci., 1986, **21**, 1057-1069
- [9] Cornie, J.A., Mortersen, A., Gungor, M.N. and Flemings, M.C., "The Solidification Process during Pressure Casting SiC and Al₂O₃ Reinforced Al-4.5%Cu Metal Matrix Composites". In 5th International Conference on Composite Metals, ed. W.C. Harrigan et al., TMS-AIME, 1985, pp.809-823
- [10] Cappleman, G.R., Watts, J.F. and Clyne, T.W., "The interface region in squeeze-infiltrated composites containing δ -alumina fibre in an aluminium matrix" J. Mat. Sci., 1985, **20**, 2159-2168
- [11] Clyne, T.W. and Mason, J.F., "The Squeeze-Infiltration Process for Fabrication of Metal-Matrix Composites", accepted for publication in submitted to Metall. Trans. A, 1987
- [12] Szekely, J., Fluid Flow Phenomena in Metal Processing, Academic, New York 1979, p.237
- [13] Sakamoto, A., Hasegawa, H. and Minoda, Y., "Mechanical Properties of SiC whisker reinforced Aluminium Composites". In 5th International Conference on Composite Materials, ed. W.C. Harrigan et al., TMS-AIME, 1985, 699-707
- [14] Clyne, T.W., "The Use of Heat Flow Modelling to Explore Solidification Phenomena", Metal. Trans. B, 1982, **13B**, 417-478
- [15] Clyne, T.W., "Modelling of Heat Flow in Solidification", Mat. Sci. & Eng., 1984, **65**, 111-124
- [16] Young, R.M.K., The Processing of Metals as Semisolid Slurries, Ph.D. Thesis, Surrey University 1986
- [17] Nieh, T.G., Rainen, R.A. and Chellman, D.J., "Microstructure and Fracture in SiC whisker reinforced 2124 Aluminium Composites". In 5th International Conference on Composite Materials, ed. W.C. Harrigan et al., TMS-AIME, 1985, 825-842
- [18] Collier, J.R. and Gunasekera, J.S., "Improved processes for the extrusion of metals and polymers", ASTM Standardisation News, Feb.1986, 45-48